

Social and Cultural Life of Pachamalai Tribes A Study

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ABSTRACT

The Pachaimalai Hills, or Pachais, are a minor mountain range in the Eastern Ghats System. They are in Tamil Nadu's Tiruchirapalli district, in southern India. It is 73 kilometres from Trichy and 112 km from Salem. The Tamil Nadu government intends to make Pachaimalai a tourism destination. It is brought to light the importance of the places in Pachamalai Hills and efforts and promotional and revival of socio-cultural development in the hills. Studies of this kind will help the people to know about the historical importance, religious significance, cultural importance and other special features of places in Pachamalai Hills.

Key Words: Malayalis, Pachamalai, Kalrayans, Kolli hills

Introduction

The Malayalis constitute an endogamous group. The descent is recognized through the male line. The life style of the Malayalis is mostly based on traditional values. As per the legends, the Malayalis migrated to the hills from Kanchipuram. To be brief three brothers namely, Periyannan, Naduannan and Chinnannan, having become outcasts accidentally left their homes, married respectively a Kaikola, a Vedan and a Palla girl and founded the settlements at Kalrayans, Pachamalai and Kolli hills. A detailed account of this legend is given in the District Gazetteer of Salem. The Malayali settlements are known by the term Ooru and the Government of India has given them the status of Scheduled Tribes. Appearance wise they are short in stature but possess sturdily built body and are dark-brown in complexion. Their hairs are black and straight. Shape of the nose varies from flat to medium with slight depression at the root. Many individuals have receding chin and thick lips¹ the tribes have a dialect of their own which is akin to the Tamil language. The dialect possesses a number of old Tamil words. Since of its uniqueness; it has been given the area dialect status²

The hill is located in the Thuraiyur taluk of the Tiruchirappalli district in Tamil Nadu. It is surrounded via Rasipuram and Namakkal in the west, in the north via Attur and Gangavalli taluk of Salem district, and in the east by means of Perambalur district. The whole hill vary is scattered over about a region of about 35, zero hectares. Its altitude levels between 2,000 and 3,000 feet. The temperature in the hill is moderate. The common most and minimal temperature in the hills are recorded as 78° F and 72°F respectively. The rainfall is additionally moderate. The common rainfall for the final three years is fifty-four inches per year States that the Kongu Country must have been the home of early man in South India It has been pointed out that the Paleolithic men did not live in the forests but on the hilly plains; and the Nilgiris, the Palanis, the Anaimalai and other hills in the Kongu Country were the primary spots where should have begun existence.

Housing Pattern

All Malayali houses are built with bamboo and covered with palm leaves and grass. The wall of the hut is made of *bamboo thatti* plastered with mud on both the sides. It has a single central room which is used both for cooking and living. There is no proper ventilation for the out let of the smoke. There is a verandah around the room, which is used as the home for pigs, goats and fowls.³ A fowl stay is in the front side of the parlour attached with the pail of the hut.

Cattle pen is just at the side of the hut. In the Kalrayans, the huts are circular and low walls are built on split bamboo daubed with clay and the roof is conical. The Pachamalai and Kolli hills tribes built their huts with the same materials as used by the Kalrayan Malayalis. But the plan of the house is rectangular.⁴The house has a high platform beneath, which there is a small compartment. Malayali house thatched of jungle grass and rags are placed to keep off the *owl* and *kotan*, the ill-omened bird. Each village is surrounded by a fence to prevent the pigs from causing destruction to the crops outside. There are few tiled houses in the traditional settlement. They are built by the government for the tribes. The tiled houses have balcony, concrete roofing etc. The mode of construction has enabled the tribes to imbibe new customs and practices.⁵ That 37.67 percent of the respondents are living in thatched houses. 25 percent of the respondents are living in concrete houses. 23 percent live in houses covered with asbestos and 14.33 percent live in tiled houses.

House hold Articles

The various household articles like basketry which are in good use among the tribes are made locally. The articles of basketry commonly used are *puttaa*(big size basket) and *kooda*(small sized basket) and *moram*(winnowing pan) Baskets are used for keeping grains whereas the winnowing pan is used to clear off the chaff during harvest and to clean the grains.⁶ To the tribes at the hills, the *vaasi* (axe) is an indispensable tool for cutting trees and felling bamboo in order to prepare the forest field into a cultivable land. The *vettaruvaa* (billhook) is used for cutting thorny and bamboo thickets etc. Hoe, locally known *kalekkoththu* is an important tool used in the slash and burn cultivation.¹¹ it is also used for clearing the surface and makes a fertile land. The *kadepaarakambi* (crow bar) it is used for digging edible roots. Almost all the tools are similar to those used by the peasants of the neighbouring villages located in the plains.⁷

Family

Family among the Malayalis is matrilineal in descent and paternal in residence. The authority in the family rests with the man who is the head of the house hold. The tribes of the hills have no attachment to any land and they do not possess any valuable property worth the name. The residence pattern among the Malayali is paternal. The man ties with marriage relationship with maternal uncle family. The marriage brings changes in the family. A man after his marriage usually moves into a separate house and lives with his spouse However, they do not like to be far away from their parents and relatives. The

composition of families in a settlement is based on kingships and that the people seek help and cooperation from one another⁸

The tribal family is divided into nuclear, immediate, extended and compound families. Majority of the tribal families are of the elementary form. In the nuclear family, the husband and wife live with married children and other kin. The joint family is also found. The Malayali family is based on cohesive bonds of kinship. Every individual in the family is set in a number of affiliations. Though patrilineage is the structural base of their society, kinship bonds exist not only with one's patrilineal kin but also with maternal kins. There is loose kinship ties between kin or one's own married sister and father's sister. It is consanguineous and affine kinship ties which frame the interpersonal relationship of their entire social organizations.⁹The kinship terminology is so structured as to make preferential cross-cousin marriage possible. Brothers and sisters are prohibited from marrying or have any sexual relation. But children of a sister and brother can marry. Again, the off springs of those unions cannot intermarry.

A man's sister's son and a woman's brother's son are equated with their daughter's husband by the terms *Marumavan* and a man's sister's daughter and women's daughter are aligned with the son's wife by the term *marumave*. Unlike parallel cousins, cross-cousins are not merged with realbrothers and sisters. A senior male parallel cousin is addressed by the term *annen* (elder brother) and a junior by the term *thambi*(younger brother). An elder female parallel cousin is addressed by the term *akkal* (elder sister). If younger the term *thangachi*(younger sister) is applied. But the terms for cross cousins are different. For instance, a mother's brother's son or father's sister's son is referred by the term *machchan*.

Kinship Ways

Patterned attitudes are seen in the context of the Malayali kinship behavior. The attitude of the parents towards children is largely ruled by affection and care. Reciprocally, the course of conduct of the children towards parents is regulated by an attitude of love and defense. They obey and respect the teachings of the parents and do not indulge in undignified acts in their presence. The unfettered spontaneous behavior of affection and defense between parents and children However, there is considerable restrain and formality when the daughter attains the age of puberty. A son associates more with his father than a daughter does in domestic activities, marketing and cultivation.¹⁰ A father shows all affection to his daughter but at the same time maintains distance. It is the moral obligation of the parents to share the social and economic responsibilities of marriage of their offspring. Married son may continue to live with his parents until his younger brother marries and unless there is paucity of

accommodation in the parental home. It is also the duty of the father to provide his married son a separate hut and some cultivable land for subsistence. Moreover though a man may live separately after his marriage, he tries to maintain cordial relations with his parents.

A man is expected to show greater respect to his parents-in-law. Father-in-law is regarded as an elder standing in relation to a man's mother's brother or father's sister's husband. A man shows much respect and cordiality to his elder sister's husband and the same behavior is practiced with regard to one's own wife's elder brother. In case of youngsters in the above kinship relation, a man is friendly towards them. The relatives visit each other's homes during rituals and render help. The pattern of kinship behavior shown by a woman towards her husband's elder brother is of almost reverence. The woman generally does not talk to her husband's elder brother. In case of younger brother of her husband, the woman speaks freely and addresses him by name and proper kinship term. The relationship between a woman and her husband's younger brother is almost similar to that between a woman and her brother.

The behavioral pattern between one man and his sister's husband is characterized by cordiality. A sister's husband has important roles in marriage and death. That is why he accompanies his wife's brother when he goes to see a prospective bride and if a man dies, it is his sister's husband who is ritually obliged to bathe the corpse.¹¹ Similar pattern of behavior is seen between a Malayali woman and her husband's sister. During marriage, a bride is attended by a sister of the bride-groom who dresses her; remain by her side all along the ritual and joins her in the marriage feast. To put it in a nutshell, it is she who helps the bride in overcoming uneasiness and shyness. The relationship between grandparents and grandchildren is marked by affectionate intimacy. Children learn glories and facts about notable incidents of the by gone days from their grandparent. The grandparents also help in reducing the tension between parents and children and heal injured feeling borne by any member at the family.

Dress

The Malayalis dress traditionally involves tucking a thaaseele cloth around their waist, covering their loins with a blanket or dhoti. They wear shirts when visiting nearby towns and wear sari for women. Elderly men wear loin-cloths in interior settlements. Women wear sari, blouses, and inner garments. The Kalrayans and Shervaroyans mostly follow traditional clothing, with women in Kolli hills wearing white cloth and covering their breasts. Pachamalai women wear kosavam and prefer colorful clothes. In Periya Kalrayans, men wear upper and lower garments, while women wear saris and blouses.

Traditional dress is disappearing, with young girls wearing modern attire due to frequent contact with non-tribes and plains people.

Customs and Habits

The tribal society is well known for its kinship system. They are all bound by traditional customs and manners. Mostly similar customs are followed by the Malayalis with regard to family life, naming of the children, period of pollution at the time of child birth and puberty, marriage and death ceremonies and religious practices.¹²

Family Life

The social life of the Malayalis center around the family setup to which members in the family are attached. The Malayalis follow the joint and nuclear family pattern. Father is the head of the family. The entire house hold work is done by women. The Malayalis have a number of children. The children are engaged in various works. As soon as a boy is married, he sets up a separate family in a newly erected house.¹³ Though physically a nuclear family is established but economically the whole family cultivates the land and share the produce. Physically they are separate but functionally joint. The number of family members varies from 2 to 9.

Marriage

The institution of marriage has been widely accepted in almost all the societies of the world. Marriage has led to the creation of the universally respected social group. As a result of marriage, the members of various communities satisfy their biological, psychological, economic and social needs. Since marriage helps the creation of a family, it has been a very important institution. It assists the time and space, covering non-literate or traditional as well as modern societies.³⁶ Marriage incurs rights, privileges and responsibilities on the marrying couple in particular and the family in general. Among the tribal's, premarital sexual intercourse between the members of the same tribe is tolerated. Premarital chastity is not an added virtue of a tribal girl. Dormitories are common feature of tribal life. Both the sexes have no separate dormitories and even if there is one, bachelors are welcome to the ladies' dormitories at any time and these dormitories serve as a place for pre-marital sexual relations and mutual understanding. Among the Badagos of Nilgiris, a man who takes a fancy to a girl is invited by her parents and made to pass the night with the girl and the next morning the girl expresses her sentiments and impressions to her parents. If the man is agreeable, she is asked to proceed in the matter. If he does not find the girl agreeable he is

equally free to walk away in the next morning. The same practice exists among the Kotas.¹⁴ The different kinds of marriages among the tribal are; marriage by exchange, marriage by service, barter marriage, marriage by purchase, bride-price marriage, marriage by capture and cross cousin marriage. The tribals value the institution of marriage very much. They regard those unmarried as socially ineffective and hence useless.¹⁵

Moy

Moy is a traditional collection of formal cash gifts given by families to celebrate marriages. Each village family and relatives of the couple from other villages must offer moy to the bride's and groom's families. The amount presented is meticulously recorded and announced aloud. Moy is usually reciprocated by the bridegroom's family or the bride's family during other weddings. The Kavundan, a traditional figure in Tamil, is seated on a mat inside a pandal, holding five betel leaves and a 'Ball of flowers' (pooppandhu). The Muppan and Kangani invite the Kavundan to the bridegroom's house for the moy. Once at the bridegroom's house, the Kavundan gives the first moy, usually in cash, amounting to one to ten rupees. Village elders then instruct the Kavundan to apply sandalwood paste on his forehead. Dinner is served in the evening.

Festive Dinner

The festive marriage feast is prepared by village women using stones and large vessels, with rice, vegetables, and cereals supplied by the bride-groom's family. The main dish is pork, which is traditionally slaughtered for every wedding. The couple then brings water from the village pond to their husband's house, where they spend three days feasting and then return to the groom's house with their best friends. The Kolli Malayali wedding involves throwing the garlands into a well, believing they float together as a good omen. After the ceremony, pan and supari are distributed, and the marriage proceedings end with a feast of pork and other food items. In the Shervaroyan hills, the bridegroom takes a modest dowry and arranges for the nalangu ceremony on the first day of the marriage. The elders of the village bless the couple, and the couple enters the village, accompanied by music. A stone representing the God is placed beneath a pandal, and flowers are distributed to the guests. The couple then walk three times around the stone, prostrate themselves, and receive blessings from the assembled elders. The ceremony ends with a feast.

Naming Ceremony

The naming ceremony is held on the pongal festival, where close relatives are served a ritual meal consisting of ragi flour, curry, and cooked rice. The mother's brother names the child, and the name is announced loudly. The child spends most of its time with its mother until its fifth year, when grandparents take care of them. The child's ear lobes are pierced by an elderly woman, and a girl's nasal septa is pierced at seven or eight years. No ceremonies are conducted for these procedures. At six years old, the boy leaves the hut and learns both indoor and outdoor folk games. Until adolescence, no sexual distinction is made, and male-female dichotomy is not pronounced.

Adolescence

Boys, as they grow, during the day time visit forests in search of honey, edible roots and hunt rabbits. But, as they became adult, they refrain from going in groups, but prefer to go individually. Even as on date, only very few children attend school. Boys over fifteen years of age start looking out to awaken to earn. Girls stay at home and attend to domestic work. As they grow up, they help the women folk of the house in the various agricultural activities fetching water and also collecting edible roots for working.¹⁶ A Pachamalai Malayali girl is considered to have attained puberty if she had her first menstruation on the contrary, only when a boy is observed with the growth of mustache and beard, he is considered to have attained age. An adult learns facts about sex from friends elder to him.¹⁷

The girls when attain age refrains from playing with boys. Menstruation frightens a girl and she keeps it as a secret and discloses it only to her mother and elder sister. During menstruation, the girl is segregated for five to seven days and made to stay in the huts already built for that purpose. These huts known as *Muttu Kudisaa* (menstruation hut) are situated away from the settlement. Women members escort her to the hut during the period. She is also given a bill book made of iron for protection against malevolent spirits. On the fifth or seventh day as the case may be, the girl is given a ritual bath in order to free her from the impurity known as *Kanni Theettu*. After the ritual bath, the girl returns to the household. On that day, a ceremonial meal with millet along with jaggery is prepared.

The parents present her with a new sari, blouse, bangles, flowers, talcum powder along with betel leaf, areca nut and parched rice. The girl is fed with ceremonial meals. After this, the girl is confined to her house for ninety days and only on ninety first day she is allowed to participate in cultural gatherings.¹⁸ Likewise, a menstruation woman is segregated in one of the huts for a period of three days

only. A woman is considered unclean during her menstruation. She refrains from cooking and served food for three days. She returns to do her normal house and performs duties following a bath on the fourth day. In the event of violation of this practice, it is believed that troubles will come. The Pachamalai Malayalis finely believe that menstruating women are prone to malevolent spirit's effects and hence such precautions are necessary.

Puberty Ceremony

A girl's puberty ceremony is called *theraty* or *sadangu*. The girl became an important member of the community and special customs are observed at the time she attained puberty. This is also mentioned by W. Francis and Edgar Thurston. When a girl attains puberty (*periyamanuchi*) immediately a message is sent to maternal uncle. The female members of the family of the maternal uncle bring jasmine flower, bananas, apples and five *karuppatticakes*. Then the maternal uncle builds a hut with fresh coconutthatches in the backyard of the house. This is called *kudichaikattal*.¹⁹ Malayalis traditionally considered a 30-day period of pollution after puberty, but now they shorten it to five days, bathe daily, and enter the house on the sixth day. The house is considered minor pollution for thirty days, and other villagers are not allowed to enter. The PeriyaMalayalis of the Shervaroyas and Kalrayans have seven to eleven days of pollution, with only a few Malayalis using Brahmin prohibit services for purification ceremonies.

Polygamy

The Pachamalai tribes are a prevalent practice often resulting from the death of the first wife or the close relationship between the husband and wife. The belief is that if the first wife gives birth to female children, the next wife will also give birth to a male child, leading to a second marriage. However, polygamy is slowly disappearing in this tribal society, with only a few instances of marriage to three women.

Old Age

When a person becomes old it is the duty of the son and daughter to take care of him. The old people are treated with respect and tenderness. They spend their time with their grandchildren. The old people are given only mild jobs such as housekeeping, caring the children etc.

Conclusion

The tribes of the hills believe that death occurs when a person becomes too old. However, they also strongly believe that magical devices such as sorcery and witchcraft can cause death. Cases of suicide and murders are also reported. As soon as a death occurs, the neighbors are informed and they come immediately.²⁰ The death ceremony in a hill tribe involves close relatives bringing paddy, koodi (waist), and garlands, and village men sending messages to other settlements. The body is displayed in a house with paddy and a lamp, and the eyes are covered with turmeric paste. The mouth is closed with a bandage, and the two thumbs and two big toes are tied together. An oil lamp is lighted by the elders, and incense sticks are burned to ward off foul smell. Messages are sent to the deceased's relatives, who are kept until they arrive. The chief mourner provides a woolen blanket to the head man and salutes him when he visits the house. The corpse is given betel leaf, areca nut, and lime, known as Muppanmeththale. The death ceremony begins with a hot water bath, decorations, garlands, coconuts, champhor, and tied to bamboo poles. The chief mourner removes the first sand of earth, goes around the grave, and cuts clothes around the toes and thumbs. Rice is thrown into the pit, and the mourners return home for a bath. The house is washed with water mixed with cow dung, and death is considered pollution. The pollution breaking ceremony occurs on the third, fifth, or seventh day, and the entire house is sprinkled with holy water. The ceremony ends with a ceremonial feast.

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